

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Hamilton**FIRST NAME:** Ertenisa**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar,

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord Microsoft 365

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Starting the Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,7-8)
2. Organizing Ideas (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,9)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,33-39)
4. Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,12-14)
5. Utilizing a Style Guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,40-42)

SCHOLARLY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Scholarly writing is a skill I have improved over the years because one of my aspirations is to add to the body of knowledge in Public Health. I have written papers and contributed to strategies and policies during my tenure as a public servant in the health sector; however, my objective assessment of my work is that it needs to be at a satisfactory academic level. This dissatisfaction has propelled me to seek out avenues that can contribute to improving my writing. As such, I felt encouraged when I discovered that the first course of the Ph.D.- Global and Health Systems ACA-401/ACA-401D focused on scholarly writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021).

The first task I started was reviewing the work of Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, which is the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1. I commend the authors on this very informative and learner-friendly document, which allowed me to comfortably add the various aspects of scholarly writing to my knowledge repository. This served as an eye-opener because the document's content also outlines the expected writing standards for a Ph.D. student. During the completion of my master's degree, I was exposed to some aspects of scholarly writing, but the details and explanations were not as thorough as what was delivered in this course.

With this paper, I will provide my perspectives on scholarly writing in the context of starting an essay, the organization of ideas, plagiarism, some rules of thumb for writing a paper, and utilizing a style guide.

2) STARTING OF AN ESSAY

Starting an essay is a task that can appear complex in the initial phases. However, it can become simplified if approached from a time management perspective. An early start is recommended because it provides a foundation for adequate time distribution, especially for collecting information on the topic, generating relevant concepts, and converting them into a well-written essay.

Formulating the research question is the subsequent task when starting an essay. The essay's body should comprise a discussion that answers this question. The question provides the basis for planning the content's capture and directs what to research.

The research process for gathering information on the topic must be logical. Writers are encouraged to begin by documenting all the information they know about the subject and then identify the gaps to solidify the argument. The gaps identified are the main pointers to what data to collect from the literature reviewed. When reviewing the various source materials, note-taking is essential. The writer should keep the research question in mind; this allows for collecting only relevant information.

After researching, the writer should review the notes, and they are encouraged to take the opportunity to organize the content of the essay, after which they can begin the writing process.

My personal view of essay writing is that you should have an idea of what you want to write about, who your audience is, and the perspective you want the audience to have on the topic. I have learned from this course that I can simplify essay writing by completing critical tasks.

3) ORGANIZING OF IDEAS

Organizing the writer's ideas is a critical task because this will ultimately answer the research question and determine how to manage the essay. The flow of the essay, the presentation of ideas, and the response to the question will either capture the attention of the reader or will cause them to lose interest (Rocco and Hatcher 2011).

Formulating a plan for the flow of the essay is essential. In this plan, the writer must address the sequence of the sentences and paragraphs. It is vital that it is aligned so that there is a logical answer to the research question. The research process will likely yield much more information than necessary, so the essay plan must guide a selection process.

4) **PLAGIARISM**

Plagiarism is an issue of ethics and the writer's principles. Your principles should dictate how you approach giving credit when using the work of others and act as a guide when affixing your name to work that is originally yours. Academic writers should understand the significance of adding to the body of knowledge and, therefore, continue to be the guardians of other writers' work when producing material.

Moreover, plagiarism can be avoided by understanding and applying citation principles. Within the context of citing, the writer must be familiar with when they can cite and when it's advisable not to cite (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 36–38). Some writers sometimes commit plagiarism without recognizing the same because of a lack of information; an example is self-plagiarism (Wong 2011, 2–3).

The in-text citation is the more complex of the two forms because writers can use multiple formats, be it quotations or paraphrasing. Quoting the exact words of an author needs to be done with care, and excessive use is discouraged because it diminishes the originality of the work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 36).

There is hope for writers, especially regarding citing in scholarly writing. Various software models are available to assist with reviewing written work. Most universities globally have included this as a part of the submission process. Review of papers by software is also a requirement of EUCLID before submission.

The takeaway from this lesson for me surrounds the topic of when not to cite. If you are using work from others, you must cite, or if you are going to make statements concerning any topic, you must cite as a demonstration that there is evidence to support your theories. However, according to Cleenewerck and Gulma in the ACA-401D Coursepack, citing is optional if the information is a common knowledge (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 37).

5) **RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER**

Adapting the recommended rule of thumb for writing a paper can become an advantage for writers of scholarly papers. Capturing and maintaining your audience of readers requires work that meets a particular standard, and this is one of the tools writers can use to meet that requirement.

The essay or paper must always include the thesis, preferably at the beginning because it establishes the context of what follows. Maintaining the focus on the proposed thesis should be the basis for the foundation laid in developing the essay. Also important is ensuring that the discussion focuses on the most relevant points (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 13).

Avoiding generalities is also crucial when writing because it can diminish the argument and cause the audience to become confused about the exact relevance of the point presented in the discussion. General statements also have the potential to deliver writing comprising a lot of content fillers and no natural substance.

A clear content presentation is essential, and it can capture the audience. It is a recommendation that sentences and paragraphs be short and concise but, at the same time, present the idea that the writer wants to capture. The writing should also have the potential to be entertaining and fun for the reader.

The onus is on the writer to approach this task earnestly and present arguments of a defined standard in recognizing that the audience is of a particular caliber. This requires meaningful research where you try as much as possible to understand the information from the writer's perspective, ultimately allowing you to articulate your point of view on the topic. There must also be additional care in ensuring that there is no plagiarism.

6) UTILIZING A STYLE GUIDE

The EUCLID has adopted the Chicago Rules (Turabian) as their recommended choice for the writing of academic papers; in addition, incorporating a style guide is also encouraged. Candidates (students) should include a style guide because it helps to develop the skills of formulating an essay plan and allows your writing to be more consistent.

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma in the ACA-401D Coursepack, the style guide provides a platform for writers to list the elements of the writing style used in their essays or papers. The style guide incorporates many necessary components that should be considered, such as paragraph numbering and indentation, the voice of the essay (active versus passive), and the use of abbreviations, amongst others.

Candidates (students) must recognize that this approach is not final, and writers are free to write according to their personal preferences.

7) CONCLUSION

This task of reading and presenting my thoughts on scholarly writing has been a very enriching experience because I had the opportunity to gain additional knowledge on this topic. Writing is one of the skills that I am deliberately working towards improving, and this course pack prepared by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma has met my expectations for this session.

I am taking away knowledge on starting a paper, organizing ideas, plagiarism, utilizing a styling guide, and, of course, the rules of thumb for writing a paper. I have applied most of what I have learned in this practical demonstration of submitting a paper on the topic.

Candidates (students) should revisit the content of this period throughout the course because repetition has the advantage of influencing change. And the anticipated change for me is scholarly writing of the highest standard.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Central African Republic.

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